

STUDIES ON THE FRIES REARRANGEMENT PART II

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Fries rearrangement has been studied with esters of sorbic acid,

In extension of our work on the Fries rearrangement of various phenolic esters of unsaturated aliphatic acids (this *Journal*, 1948, 26, 393), the present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the Fries migration of phenolic esters of sorbic acid, which has a pair of conjugated double bonds in the molecule.

Four esters of sorbic acid, with phenol and *o*-, *m*-, *p*-cresol have been prepared. The main rearrangement products, in these cases also, were *o*-hydroxy-ketones (about 50-55%), which have been characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sorbic acid was obtained from crotonaldehyde (40 g.) malonic acid (60 g.) in 60 c.c. of pyridine in 24 g. yield on following the method of Doebner (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 2140), m. p. 134-35°.

Chloride of Sorbic Acid.—Sorbic acid (20 g.), suspended in dry petrol ether (200 c.c.), was taken in a three-necked flask, fitted with a mechanical stirrer, a dropping funnel and a reflux condenser. Thionyl chloride (42.6 g.) was added to it dropwise when a brisk evolution of hydrogen chloride took place. The mixture was then refluxed on the water-bath for 3 hours. The excess of thionyl chloride and petrol ether were distilled off on the water-bath and the residual acid chloride distilled under reduced pressure, b. p. 83°/3 mm., yield 22 g.

Doebner (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 2221) prepared the acid chloride by the action of phosphorus pentachloride on the acid, b. p. 78°/15 mm. The lower boiling point obtained by him was probably due to the acid chloride being contaminated with phosphorus oxychloride, which is formed during the course of the reaction.

Phenyl Ester of Sorbic Acid.—To phenol (5.7 g.) was gradually added sorbic acid chloride (8 g.) and the mixture heated under reflux on a water-bath till the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased. After cooling and addition of water the ester separated out as an oil which was extracted with ether, washed with 1% sodium hydroxide and then finally with water. After dehydration, the ether was distilled off and the ester distilled under reduced pressure, b. p. 141°/2 mm., yield 7.5 g. (Found: C, 76.11; H, 6.53. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 76.59; H, 6.38 per cent).

o-Cresyl ester of sorbic acid was prepared as above from the acid chloride (7 g.) and *o*-cresol (5.7 g.), yield 6.6 g., b. p. 143°/4 mm. (Found: C, 76.91; H, 7.05. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires, C, 77.22; H, 6.93 per cent).

m-Cresyl ester of sorbic acid was prepared in the usual manner from the acid chloride (9 g.) and *m*-cresol (7.2 g.), yield 10 g., b. p. 180°/17 mm. (Found: C, 76.85; H, 7.12. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 77.22; H, 6.93 per cent).

p-Cresyl ester of sorbic acid was prepared as above from the acid chloride (9 g.) and *p*-cresol (7.2 g.), as shining white crystals from ether, m. p. 73°-74°, yield 11 g. (Found: C, 77.68; H, 6.46. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 77.22; H, 6.93 per cent).

Fries Rearrangement of the above Esters.—The ester (0.031 mole) was added gradually to finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.047 mole) taken in a 250 c.c. flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a dropping funnel. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours at 100°. To the reddish crystalline mass formed, dilute hydrochloric acid was added. The oil separating was taken up in ether, washed successively with water, 1% sodium carbonate solution and finally with water. After dehydration over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether was distilled off and the residue distilled under reduced pressure. The distillate conformed to Pyman's test (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280) for *o*-hydroxy ketones.

These ketones, thus obtained, were all converted into their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones which were recrystallised from toluene.

TABLE I

Products of the Fries rearrangement of the above esters.

<i>o</i> -Hydroxy-ketones.	B. p.	Dinitrophenylhydrazone		% Nitrogen	
		M. p.	Mol. formula.	Found	Calc
(a)	83°/3 mm.	220°	$C_{18}H_{16}O_5N_4$	14.83%	15.21%
(b)	103°/1	209°	$C_{19}H_{18}O_5N_4$	14.41	14.65
(c)	122°/17	212°	—	14.98	—
(d)	150°/10	208°	—	14.84	—

(a) = 2'-Hydroxyphenyl- Δ^2 - Δ^4 -hexadiene-one-1

(b) = 2'-Hydroxy-3'-methylphenyl- Δ^2 - Δ^4 -hexadiene-one-1

(c) = 2'-Hydroxy-4'-methylphenyl- Δ^2 - Δ^4 -hexadiene-one-1

(d) = 2'-Hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl- Δ^2 - Δ^4 -hexadiene-one-1

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